

Quadrant Vacancy Prompting: Targeting Blank Regions in AI-Labeled 2×2 Semantic Maps to Steer Large Language Models Beyond Typical Responses

二軸四象限マップの「空白地帯」を狙い撃つ：LLM の典型解バイアスを回避する発想支援手法 Quadrant Vacancy Prompting (QVP) の提案

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Abstract

Large language models (LLMs) tend to concentrate their outputs around semantically similar “typical” answers even when repeatedly prompted on the same theme—a phenomenon documented as post-alignment mode collapse and output homogenization. Neither repeated chat sampling nor reasoning-enhancement techniques such as Chain-of-Thought reliably expand the *breadth* of ideation. This paper proposes **Quadrant Vacancy Prompting (QVP)**, a practical method that (1) has an LLM generate a large set (tens to hundreds) of answers to a theme, (2) has the LLM itself label two evaluation axes and map all answers onto the resulting 2×2 plane, (3) repeatedly re-maps the answers under newly generated axis pairs, (4) identifies *vacancies*—blank regions ranging from entire quadrants to smaller local gaps—and (5) verbalizes the coordinates of a vacancy as explicit constraints in a new generation prompt, forcing the model to produce answers that fill the gap. We show that QVP is structurally analogous to filling unreached cells in Quality-Diversity search, to vacancy analysis in keyword-based patent maps, and to Boden’s transformational creativity, and we argue that conditioning on vacancy coordinates operates as a forced shift of the generation distribution from its mode toward its tails. We illustrate the method with a case study conducted on ProAI Studio, a card-based ideation application (theme: new services to reduce food waste), in which all ten vacancy-targeted generations landed in the designated blank quadrant and both an opportunity-type (“blue ocean”) and a worthless (“dead ocean”) vacancy emerged within a single coordinate system. We further present an evaluation protocol for systematic empirical validation.

Keywords: large language models; ideation support; quality-diversity; mode collapse; 2×2 matrix; white-space analysis; human-AI co-creation; prompting

1. Introduction

1.1 Background: LLMs are weak at breadth

While LLMs raise the productivity of individual creative work, it has been repeatedly reported that their outputs resemble one another. Doshi & Hauser (2024) showed that stories written with GPT-4 idea support were rated higher than solo-written ones, yet similarity *between* stories increased—a loss of collective diversity. Anderson, Shah & Kreminski (2024) found that groups ideating with ChatGPT produced more homogenized idea sets at the group level than groups using a non-AI tool (Oblique Strategies cards). Padmakumar & He (2024) likewise reported that writing assistance from instruction-tuned LLMs reduces lexical and content diversity.

The root of this homogenization lies in the training process itself. Kirk et al. (2024) demonstrated that RLHF (reinforcement learning from human feedback) substantially reduces output diversity, and Mohammadi (2024) analyzed how aligned models collapse onto a small number of “attractor states.” Zhang et al. (2025) further showed that a *typicality bias* in preference data—annotators favoring familiar-looking text—is a root cause of mode collapse. In short, modern LLMs are optimized by design to return **the mode of the probability distribution, i.e., the most typical answer**; even when a user repeatedly asks for “another idea,” the model does not easily reach the atypical answers in the tails of the distribution.

1.2 Problem: searching in depth and searching in breadth are different

Reasoning-enhancement methods such as Chain-of-Thought (Wei et al., 2022) and Tree of Thoughts (Yao et al., 2023) deepen and sharpen the path toward *one* answer; they are not techniques for systematically exploring the *breadth* of the answer space. No matter how deep the reasoning goes, if the underlying generation distribution is biased toward typical answers, the search unfolds in the neighborhood of those typical answers. What open-ended tasks such as ideation, planning, and strategy truly require is a mechanism for **deliberately stepping into regions that no one—including the model itself—has yet verbalized**.

1.3 Proposal and origin

The core intuition behind QVP is simple: **when a large set of LLM-generated answers is turned into a map, the places where no answers exist become visible—and those places are candidate unexplored regions lying outside the model’s typical-answer bias**.

Concretely, the answer set is arranged on a 2-axis, 4-quadrant plane. The axis labels themselves are generated by the LLM from the theme, and the answers are re-mapped repeatedly under different axis pairs. Under some coordinate system, a region with no answers appears—sometimes an entire quadrant, sometimes a smaller local “vacancy.” When the coordinates of that vacancy (e.g., “high on axis X, low on axis Y”) are verbalized as explicit constraints in a new prompt for the original theme, the model produces answers that are difficult to reach through ordinary chat exchanges or through the LLM’s own reasoning. This is QVP.

The author noticed this phenomenon through consulting practice using ProAI Studio (ProAI Inc.), an ideation-support application that externalizes ideas as cards and arranges them spatially. The purpose of this paper is to (a) situate this practical insight in the context of existing research, (b) explain its working mechanism theoretically, and (c) formalize it as a reproducible procedure with an evaluation protocol.

1.4 Contributions

1. We formalize QVP, an ideation-support method that converts blank regions of AI-labeled 2×2 maps into generation constraints, as a reproducible procedure.
2. We explain its working principle from three perspectives: (i) a forced shift of the generation distribution from mode to tails; (ii) structural identity with filling unreached cells in Quality-Diversity search; and (iii) the lineage of white-space analysis in patent maps and business strategy.
3. We classify vacancies into opportunity-type (“blue ocean”) and worthless-type (“dead ocean”), and formalize a triage heuristic based on the valence of axis poles.
4. We report a case study on ProAI Studio (theme: reducing food waste; 20 initial ideas, the emergence of vacancies through axis re-labeling, and 10 vacancy-filling ideas), contrasted with ordinary chat responses.
5. We present an evaluation protocol (baselines, metrics, procedures) for validating the method.

2. Related Work

2.1 Homogenization and mode collapse in LLM outputs

As noted above, homogenization has been confirmed at the group level (Anderson et al., 2024; Doshi & Hauser, 2024), in individual writing processes (Padmakumar & He, 2024), and in the model’s internal generation distribution (Kirk et al., 2024; Mohammadi, 2024). Proposed mitigations include decoding adjustments such as temperature, and prompting techniques such as Verbalized Sampling (Zhang et al., 2025), which asks the model to verbalize multiple answers with their probabilities. These are *probabilistic* approaches that raise the chance of sampling from the tails. QVP is an orthogonal, *structural* approach: it uses the spatial arrangement of already-obtained samples to name **a specific coordinate within the tails** and steer generation there. The two families are composable.

2.2 Quality-Diversity search

In evolutionary computation, Quality-Diversity (QD) algorithms pursue quality and diversity simultaneously—e.g., Novelty Search, which abandons the objective function and rewards novelty alone (Lehman & Stanley, 2011), and MAP-Elites, which keeps the best solution per cell of a feature-space grid (Mouret & Clune, 2015). In MAP-Elites, filling cells that contain no solution yet (unreached cells) drives the search. QDAIF (Bradley et al., 2024) replaced both the definition of feature dimensions and the evaluation of quality with LLM-based AI feedback, and showed improved coverage of the search space in creative-writing domains.

QVP can be positioned as a transplantation of the QD idea into chat-based ideation. The correspondence is direct: two axes = feature dimensions (behavior descriptors); quadrants or local regions = cells; vacancies = unreached cells; vacancy-targeted generation = mutation/generation into unreached cells. QVP’s distinctive features are threefold: (a) the feature dimensions (axis labels) themselves are dynamically named and re-named by the LLM each round; (b) instead of a machine-run evolutionary loop, it is a lightweight human-in-the-loop procedure in which a person looks at the map and selects a vacancy; and (c) the human interpretation of what a vacancy *means* is itself treated as a source of ideation value.

2.3 Structured exploration of LLM design spaces (HCI)

In HCI, motivated by the concern that one-question-one-answer chat causes premature convergence on a few ideas, interfaces that structure the response space have been proposed. Luminare (Suh et al., 2024) first has the LLM generate “dimensions” from a prompt, then systematically generates and arranges responses by combinations of dimensions so that writers can survey and explore the design space. Sensecape (Suh et al., 2023) supports multilevel exploration and sensemaking. QVP belongs to this lineage, but differs in emphasis: where Luminare focuses on *filling* the space through dimensions, QVP treats the *blanks that remain after filling* as the primary information resource and centers its loop on converting blanks into generation constraints.

2.4 The lineage of discovering opportunity in blanks

The heuristic “a blank on the map = an opportunity” has established precedents across fields. In technology management, Lee, Yoon & Park (2009) defined large, sparse regions of keyword-based patent maps as *patent vacancies* and proposed extracting and validating them as candidate opportunities for new technology creation; white-space analysis is likewise standard practice in patent analytics. In business strategy, Blue Ocean Strategy (Kim & Mauborgne, 2005) offered a framework for discovering uncontested market space by re-drawing the axes of competition, and the 2×2 matrix has been a basic language of strategy since Ansoff’s (1957) growth matrix. In sociology, Burt (2004) showed that individuals near *structural holes* in social networks produce better ideas. In the Japanese tradition of ideation methods, Kawakita’s (1967)

KJ method has long been practiced as a way of letting new structures emerge from the spatial arrangement and labeling of information fragments.

QVP’s novelty lies in repurposing this “blank = opportunity” heuristic into a closed loop in which **the data, the axes of the map, and the blank-filling generation are all performed by an LLM**, applied to circumventing the LLM’s own typical-answer bias. Where patent white-space analysis searches for technologies that do not yet exist in the world, QVP searches for answers that *this LLM* has not (or barely can) generate for this theme. The former’s blanks reflect the state of the world; the latter’s reflect the shape of the model’s generation distribution.

2.5 Connection to creativity theory

Boden (2004) distinguishes creativity as exploration within a conceptual space (exploratory creativity) from creativity that changes the rules of the space itself (transformational creativity). In QVP, “filling vacancies within a fixed axis pair” corresponds to the former, and “re-mapping by re-labeling the axes” to the latter; QVP can thus be read as a procedural implementation that alternates exploratory and transformational creativity. Gärdenfors’s (2000) theory of conceptual spaces represents concepts as regions in geometric spaces spanned by quality dimensions; QVP’s 2-axis plane can be regarded as a deliberately low-dimensional working approximation of such spaces. Restricting the dimensionality to two loses information—but it is also precisely what allows a human to see the blank.

3. Proposed Method: Quadrant Vacancy Prompting (QVP)

3.1 Overview and core hypothesis

The core hypothesis of QVP is as follows.

Hypothesis (vacancy = low-probability specification): When a large set of LLM-generated answers to a theme T is arranged on a plane whose two axes are named by an AI, the coordinates of regions containing no answers represent “specifications of answers that are semantically describable but have low probability under the model’s typical generation distribution.” Conditioning generation on these coordinates, expressed as verbal constraints, yields atypical answers that are hard to reach via ordinary sampling or reasoning enhancement.

3.2 Procedure

QVP consists of six steps. We assume N (number of answers) in the tens to hundreds and K (number of re-mappings) of roughly 3–10.

Step 1 (Mass generation). Given theme T, have the LLM generate N answers. To secure diversity, raising temperature, varying personas, or Verbalized Sampling may be combined.

Step 2 (Axis naming). Present the answer set to the LLM and instruct: “Name two mutually independent evaluation axes, with labels for both poles, that best discriminate among these answers.” Example (theme “a new breakfast service”): X-axis = time efficiency (quick \rightleftharpoons leisurely); Y-axis = sociality (solo \rightleftharpoons communal).

Step 3 (Mapping). Have the LLM assign each answer a score on both axes (e.g., -1.0 to $+1.0$) and place it on the plane.

Step 4 (Vacancy detection). Identify regions where answers are absent or extremely sparse. Two granularities exist: **quadrant vacancies** (an entire quadrant blank or near-blank) and **local vacancies** (smaller gaps inside quadrants or near axis boundaries, e.g., only the band “X high, Y slightly high” is missing).

Step 5 (Re-mapping). Return to Step 2 and have the LLM name a different axis pair; rearrange. Repeat K times. Regions of answer space that correspond to vacancies under multiple coordinate systems are treated as “robust vacancies” and prioritized (Section 3.4).

Step 6 (Vacancy-filling generation). Convert the coordinates of the chosen vacancy into verbal constraints and prompt with theme T, e.g.: “For the theme ‘a new breakfast service,’ generate 10 proposals that are **extremely time-efficient and also highly communal**, semantically non-overlapping with the existing N answers.” Map the results again to confirm they actually fill the vacancy (if they do not—or if only low-value answers result—the vacancy is likely worthless-type; Section 3.3).

A variant performs Steps 2–4 with sentence embeddings (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019) and dimensionality reduction instead of LLM scoring. AI-named axes, however, carry human-interpretable labels, which connect directly to the verbalization of constraints in Step 6.

3.3 Two types of vacancy: blue ocean and dead ocean

Not every vacancy is an opportunity. At minimum, two types must be distinguished.

- **Opportunity-type vacancy (“blue ocean”):** semantically realizable, but never generated because of the typical-answer bias. Filling it yields atypical *and* useful answers. It is blank *because no one has found it yet*.
- **Worthless-type vacancy (“dead ocean”):** filling attempts yield only low-value answers. This covers both regions that are blank *because no one needs them* and regions where the axis-value combination is semantically incompatible so that filling cannot succeed at all (e.g., “minimal cost” and “fully bespoke”).

This distinction is structurally the same as the procedure of Lee et al. (2009), who validate patent-map vacancies against technological importance and trends, and it matches the implication of Blue Ocean Strategy (Kim & Mauborgne, 2005) that not every uncontested space is promising.

As a triage cue, the **valence of the axis poles** can be used. When one pole of an axis is normatively negative for the theme (e.g., “reactive/passive”), a vacancy on that side is likely a dead ocean—blank merely because it is inferior and therefore never chosen. Conversely, vacancies that appear under axis pairs whose poles are all neutral and descriptive are relatively more likely to be opportunity-type. Final judgment rests with human evaluation (optionally combined with AI evaluation); in the author’s practice, this judgment can usually be made instantly and intuitively at a glance at the map (an example is given in Section 5.2). Even a worthless vacancy can have by-product value: verbalizing *why* it is blank can surface hidden constraints and assumptions.

3.4 The dual role of re-mapping

Re-labeling the axes plays two roles. First, **expansion of the search range:** one coordinate system is only one projection of the answer set, and each new axis pair makes different vacancies visible. Second, **a robustness test for vacancies:** if a vacancy appears only under one particular axis pair, it may be an artifact of that coordinate system; but if semantically nearby regions repeatedly come up blank under several independent coordinate systems, that region is likely genuinely low-density in the model’s generation distribution. Re-mapping is thus simultaneously an operation of Boden’s transformational creativity (changing the rules of the space) and a denoising of the vacancy signal.

4. Why Do Vacancies Work? Theoretical Considerations

4.1 The probability-distribution view: a forced shift from mode to tails

LLM generation for theme T is sampling from a conditional distribution $p(y | T)$. In aligned models this distribution is sharply peaked around typical answers (Kirk et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2025); even N samples cluster into a few semantic groups. A vacancy on the map is the “outside” of this cluster structure, made visible in a humanly interpretable two-dimensional coordinate system.

The filling generation of Step 6 amounts to sampling from $p(y | T, c)$, where c is the verbal constraint corresponding to the vacancy coordinates. Because c names a combination of properties that the typical answers do *not* satisfy, this conditioning shifts probability mass from the mode toward the tails. Crucially, whereas raising temperature spreads probability *indiscriminately* across all tails, QVP first identifies *which* tail is empty from the observed arrangement of samples and then shifts the distribution *toward that specific direction*.

4.2 The search view: a pseudo-MAP-Elites via prompting

The operation in 4.1 is isomorphic to MAP-Elites (Mouret & Clune, 2015) filling unreached cells of a feature-space grid. As QDAIF (Bradley et al., 2024) showed, both the definition of feature dimensions and the evaluation can be delegated to LLMs; QVP further delegates “cell selection” to human (or AI) vacancy recognition and performs “generation into the cell” with constraint-conditioned prompting. In place of an evolutionary loop, the human act of reading the map and interpreting what the blank means functions as the search heuristic. QVP can thus be seen as **a minimal implementation of QD search for the chat interface**.

4.3 The cognitive view: creativity through constraints and externalization

Creativity research has repeatedly observed that well-chosen constraints outperform “think freely.” Vacancy coordinates are constraints that are automatically derived from the theme and *guaranteed to be unexplored*—a particularly high-value kind of constraint. Moreover, externalizing the answer set as a map enables, as the KJ method (Kawakita, 1967) has long demonstrated, the perception of global structure—bias, density, absence—that cannot be seen by reading answers one by one. A vacancy is not an answer but a **pattern of absence in the answer set**, information that is in principle imperceptible without externalization.

4.4 Relation to reasoning enhancement: orthogonality of depth and breadth

CoT (Wei et al., 2022) and ToT (Yao et al., 2023) raise the quality of a solution to a given question through deeper reasoning. QVP instead secures breadth by recombining the constraints attached to the question. The two are orthogonal, and a natural combination is to apply CoT/ToT to the filling generation for a vacancy identified by QVP. The reason an LLM’s solo reasoning rarely reaches the vacancies is that its search tree unfolds according to the generation distribution and is therefore not free of the underlying typical-answer bias. QVP replaces **the distribution at the starting point of reasoning** itself.

5. Case Study: Execution on ProAI Studio

This chapter reports one case in which the proposed method was executed on the ideation-support application ProAI Studio (ProAI Inc.). The case is an illustration of how the method behaves and how vacancies appear, not a controlled experiment; its status and limitations are discussed in Section 5.5.

5.1 Setup

The case was run on June 10, 2026. The application was ProAI Studio, which generates and externalizes ideas as cards arranged on a 2-axis, 4-quadrant board. ChatGPT 5.5 was used for everything: idea generation, axis-label proposal, and card re-placement. The theme was “**a new service to reduce food waste.**” Scale: 20 initial ideas, one axis re-labeling ($K = 1$), and 10 vacancy-filling generations.

5.2 Procedure and course of events

Initial mapping (Figures 1–2). The initial axes were a general-purpose pair the author has long used in ideation work since his years at an advertising agency: horizontal “worm’s-eye view (micro, on-the-ground) \rightleftharpoons bird’s-eye view (macro, overview)” and vertical “logical (realistic) \rightleftharpoons magical (visionary).” Under these axes, the 20 generated cards spread fairly evenly across all four quadrants (Figure 2); no significant vacancy was observed in this coordinate system. The magical side held visionary, poetic ideas (e.g., “A town that eats its margins,” “A lighthouse for leftovers”), the logical side practical ones (e.g., “Reservation-based purchase before expiry,” “Visualizing household stock”).

Figure 1. Initial state: the general-purpose axes “worm’s-eye \rightleftharpoons bird’s-eye” \times “logical \rightleftharpoons magical” and the theme card (ProAI Studio).

Figure 2. Distribution of the 20 ideas under the initial axes. The cards spread across all four quadrants; no significant vacancy.

Re-mapping and the emergence of vacancies (Figure 3). Next, the AI was asked to propose a new axis pair based on the content of the 20 ideas. It proposed horizontal “reactive/passive (受け身) \rightleftharpoons proactive (能動)” and vertical “point-level response (点対応) \rightleftharpoons system-level design (面設計).” Re-arranged in this coordinate system, the distribution changed completely. The cards concentrated along a diagonal band connecting “system-level \times proactive” (upper right: visionary designs of town-wide food circulation) and “point-level \times reactive” (lower left: after-the-fact responses such as discounting, brokering, and stock visualization of surplus that has already occurred), leaving the **lower-right quadrant (proactive \times point-level) almost completely blank.**

The upper-left quadrant (reactive \times system-level) was also sparse. The author ran the same 10-idea filling generation on the upper left as well (full Japanese texts in Appendix D); the resulting answers amounted to repetitions of ideas close to existing food-bank and regional-coordination initiatives that passively absorb surplus at the regional level. Most strikingly, the titles of the 10 ideas converged on near-identical paraphrases of one another (“absorbing/catching surplus/leftovers at the regional/area level”)—in sharp contrast to the 10 lower-right ideas generated by the identical procedure, whose titles and mechanisms were varied. This suggests that in a worthless vacancy, even forced coordinates leave the model with essentially one idea’s worth of content to offer. “Reactive/passive” is a normatively negative pole for this theme; this vacancy is blank merely because it is inferior and was never chosen—an instance of the worthless-type (dead-ocean) vacancy of Section 3.3. By contrast, both poles of the lower-right “proactive \times point-level” are neutral and descriptive, and the author judged it a candidate opportunity-type (blue-ocean) vacancy and selected it for filling. This triage was made instantly, by intuition, at a glance at the map. As a result, this single case exhibited both vacancy types of Section 3.3 within one coordinate system.

Figure 3. Re-arrangement under the AI-proposed axes “reactive \rightleftharpoons proactive” \times “point-level \rightleftharpoons system-level.”The cards concentrate along the lower-left-to-upper-right diagonal band, leaving the lower-right quadrant (proactive \times point-level) blank.

The fact that the same 20 ideas showed no vacancy under the initial axes but a clear vacancy under different axes concretely demonstrates that vacancies are not a fixed property inherent in the answer set but arise in interaction with the coordinate system—and therefore that axis re-labeling is an indispensable operation for vacancy discovery (Section 3.4).

Vacancy-filling generation (Figure 4). Designating the lower-right quadrant (proactive \times point-level), 10 additional ideas were generated for the same theme. Their titles (English glosses): “Act before surplus arises,”“Create the buyer first,”“Sell without waiting for surplus,”“Sell out before anything is left over,”“Sell surplus pre-emptively,”“Gather buyers in advance,”“Instant matching of surplus items,”“Capture the eaters first,”and “Sell out food loss via reservations”(two ideas with this title). Full Japanese texts are in Appendix B. Upon re-placement, all 10 ideas landed inside the designated lower-right quadrant.

Figure 4. Vacancy-filling generation targeting the lower-right quadrant. The orange cards are the 10 newly generated ideas; all were placed inside the designated quadrant.

5.3 Characteristics of the vacancy-filling answers

The 10 ideas share a clear common structure: **an inversion of the time axis—from “processing surplus after it occurs” to “securing buyers and sales channels before surplus occurs.”** Concrete mechanisms include (a) selling advance-reservation slots based on leftover prediction; (b) demand-side-first designs in which users pre-register purchase intent (pickup time, price range, location) and stores push individual offers to matching users (“Capture the eaters first”); and (c) adjusting production volume itself based on reservation counts, reducing overproduction at the source. All of them substantively satisfy the constraint encoded by the vacancy coordinates: proactive (not waiting for surplus to occur) and point-level (realized at the level of individual stores, transactions, and moments).

In fairness, the initial 20 ideas contained one adjacent seed, “Reservation-based purchase before expiry.” The explicit designation of the vacant quadrant, however, sharpened this direction into a consistent design principle—“create demand first”—and unfolded it into a coherent cluster of 10 ideas. In this case, vacancy filling functioned less as creation ex nihilo than as **an operation that amplifies a weak signal at the edge of the answer distribution by naming its coordinates.**

5.4 Contrast with ordinary chat

On the same day, ChatGPT (ordinary chat UI) was asked for 10 ideas on the identical theme (full Japanese text in Appendix C). The results were: “AI ingredient sharing,” “Receipt-linked fridge app,” “Subscription rescue-vegetable box,” “Dynamic discounting AI,” “Corporate-cafeteria matching,” “Uber for food loss,” “AI demand-forecast SaaS,” “Eat-it-all point economy,” “Food-loss auction,” and “AI meal-planning agent.”

	Ordinary chat (Appendix C)	Vacancy filling (Appendix B)
Representative titles	Dynamic discounting AI; Food-loss auction; AI demand-forecast SaaS; etc.	Sell out before anything is left over; Gather buyers in advance; Capture the eaters first; etc.
Dominant paradigm	After-the-fact processing of occurred surplus (discounting, redistribution, delivery), or system-level prediction/management	Locking in demand before surplus occurs (advance reservations, pre-registered purchase intent, production adjustment)
Temporal structure	Surplus occurs → respond	Secure demand → surplus avoided

Table 1. Comparison of ordinary chat answers and vacancy-filling answers.

Most of the ordinary-chat ideas fall under after-the-fact circulation, discounting, and redistribution of occurred surplus, or under system-level prediction and inventory management, and resemble existing categories of food-waste services. This concretely instantiates, for this theme, the typical-answer cluster discussed in Section 1.1. Conversely, the “secure demand first at the individual-transaction level” type that characterized the vacancy-filling ideas was absent from the ordinary-chat ten. This contrast, however, does not control for prompt wording, conversational context, or generation settings; it is offered strictly as an illustration.

5.5 Limitations of this case

This case is a single theme and a single run. Its limitations: (a) the axes were re-labeled only once, so the multi-coordinate robustness test of Section 3.4 was not performed; (b) judgments of novelty and usefulness rest on the author’s qualitative evaluation; (c) card placement is itself an LLM judgment and may contain error; (d) the comparison condition is uncontrolled. Systematic validation following the protocol of Chapter 6 remains future work.

6. Evaluation Protocol (Proposed)

We propose the following design for validating QVP.

Comparison conditions (baselines): (a) simple repeated sampling (same prompt, N items); (b) high-temperature sampling; (c) persona-varied prompting; (d) Verbalized Sampling (Zhang et al., 2025); (e) Luminare-style dimension-filling generation (Suh et al., 2024); (f) QVP (proposed).

Tasks: 10–20 ideation themes from multiple domains (e.g., new business, product concepts, research topics, solutions to social problems).

Primary metrics:

- Novelty (distributional):** embedding distance (nearest-neighbor and mean) between each condition’s outputs and a large corpus from baseline (a); measures the degree to which QVP outputs fall outside the baseline clusters.
- Diversity (collective):** mean pairwise distance within each condition; coverage (occupied-cell ratio on axis grids).
- Quality:** blinded human ratings of usefulness, feasibility, and surprisingness by multiple raters. To discriminate novel-but-worthless answers (products of dead-ocean vacancies), novelty and usefulness must be rated independently.
- Fill success rate:** the proportion of generated items that are re-mapped into the designated vacancy coordinates.

Confounds to control: self-evaluation bias when the same model performs mapping, axis naming, and filling (use separate judge models and human raters); reproducibility of LLM scoring (report re-scoring agreement); and total generation-token budget (QVP requires N preliminary generations, so equalize compute across conditions).

Preregistration: hypotheses, metrics, and exclusion criteria should be preregistered to suppress confirmation bias.

7. Limitations and Discussion

1. **Lack of validation:** the empirical support in this paper is limited to the single-case illustration of Chapter 5; controlled experiments remain future work.
 2. **Dependence on axis quality:** the information content of a vacancy depends on the discriminative power of the axes. If the LLM names trite, redundant, or correlated axes, vacancies carry no meaning. Automatic evaluation of axis independence and interpretability is future work.
 3. **Mapping error:** the coordinates assigned to answers are LLM judgments containing noise and systematic error; a vacancy may always be an artifact of placement error (the robustness test via re-mapping is only a partial remedy).
 4. **The cost of worthless vacancies:** not every vacancy is an opportunity (Section 3.3). We presented an intuitive triage based on axis valence together with a real instance, but systematic evaluation of the reliability of this judgment, and its automation, remain open.
 5. **Reduction to two dimensions:** the two axes are projections of a high-dimensional semantic space; a blank on the plane does not necessarily mean a blank in the high-dimensional space, and points adjacent on the plane may be distant in it. Re-mapping under many coordinate systems partially mitigates this.
 6. **Scope:** QVP targets open-ended ideation, planning, and strategy tasks, not problems with a single correct answer (calculation, factual questions).
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8. Conclusion

This paper proposed Quadrant Vacancy Prompting: repeatedly re-arranging a large set of LLM-generated answers on AI-labeled 2×2 maps and converting the blank regions that appear into generation constraints, thereby eliciting answers that lie outside the LLM’s typical-answer bias. A vacancy is the cartographic trace of “what the model has not yet said,” and verbalizing its coordinates operates as a targeted shift of the generation distribution from mode to tails. The method sits at the intersection of three independent lineages—Quality-Diversity search, patent white-space analysis, and transformational creativity—each of which corroborates its working principle. Future work includes empirical validation under the proposed protocol and the automation of vacancy detection and triage.

Conflict of Interest

The author is the chief executive officer of ProAI Inc., which develops and provides the ideation-support application ProAI Studio referred to in this paper.

Data and Code Availability

The full texts of all outputs generated in the Chapter 5 case study are reproduced (in the original Japanese) in Appendices B–D of the companion Japanese-language version of this paper,

contained in the same Zenodo record (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20627544>). Appendix A below provides English renderings of the prompt templates.

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Appendix A: Example Prompt Templates

The templates below are English renderings; the original practice was conducted in Japanese.

A.1 Mass generation (Step 1)

Theme: "{theme}"

Generate {N} candidate answers to this theme, each as different in conception from the others as possible.
Each answer in 1–2 sentences, numbered.

A.2 Axis naming (Step 2)

Below is a set of answers to the theme "{theme}".

{answer list}

Propose the two evaluation axes that best discriminate among these answers. Conditions:

- The two axes must be conceptually independent of each other.
- Each axis must have labels for both poles (e.g., quick \neq leisurely).
- The pair must differ in perspective from previously used pairs ({list of used axes}).

Output format: X-axis: {neg} \neq {pos} / Y-axis: {neg} \neq {pos}

A.3 Mapping (Step 3)

Assign each answer a score from -1.0 to +1.0 on the X-axis ({X definition}) and the Y-axis ({Y definition}).

Output format: answer number, X score, Y score (CSV).

Always output a number even when uncertain, with a one-line rationale.

A.4 Vacancy-filling generation (Step 6)

Theme: "{theme}"

Arranging the answers so far on the X-axis ({X definition}) and the Y-axis ({Y definition}), no answers exist in the region

"{vacancy condition, e.g., $X \geq +0.5$ and Y between -0.3 and $+0.3$ "}.

Generate {M} proposals that simultaneously satisfy this vacancy condition. Conditions:

- Do not semantically overlap the existing answers ({a few representative examples}).
- Satisfy the vacancy condition substantively, not by superficial rephrasing.
- Append a one-line explanation of why each proposal satisfies the condition.

Appendix B: The 10 Vacancy-Filling Ideas (Opportunity-Type, Lower-Right Quadrant)

Generated by designating the lower-right quadrant (proactive \times point-level). Titles with English glosses; the full original Japanese texts are reproduced in Appendix B of the companion Japanese-language version in this Zenodo record.

B.1 余りを待たず動く—Act before surplus arises B.2 売り先を先に作る—Create the buyer first B.3 余剰を待たず売る—Sell without waiting for surplus B.4 余る前に売り切る—Sell out before anything

is left over B.5 余剰を先回りで売る—Sell surplus pre-emptively B.6 買い手を先に集める—Gather buyers in advance B.7 余剰品即時マッチ—Instant matching of surplus items B.8 食べ手を先に捕まえる—Capture the eaters first B.9 予約で売切る食品ロス—Sell out food loss via reservations (1) B.10 予約で売切る食品ロス—Sell out food loss via reservations (2)

Appendix C: The 10 Ordinary-Chat Ideas (Baseline)

Obtained from ChatGPT (ordinary chat UI) on the same day and theme. Titles with English glosses; full original Japanese text in Appendix C of the companion Japanese-language version.

C.1 AI 食材シェアリング—AI ingredient sharing C.2 冷蔵庫レシート連携アプリ—Receipt-linked fridge app C.3 サブスク型レスキュー野菜 BOX —Subscription rescue-vegetable box C.4 ダイナミック値引き AI —Dynamic discounting AI C.5 社員食堂マッチング—Corporate-cafeteria matching C.6 食品ロス版 Uber —Uber for food loss C.7 AI 需要予測 SaaS —AI demand-forecast SaaS C.8 食べきりポイント経済圏—Eat-it-all point economy C.9 フードロス・オークション—Food-loss auction C.10 AI 献立エージェント—AI meal-planning agent

Appendix D: The 10 Dead-Ocean Ideas (Worthless-Type, Upper-Left Quadrant)

Generated by designating the upper-left quadrant (reactive × system-level). Note how the ten titles converge on near-identical paraphrases of a single idea—observable evidence of the worthless-type vacancy. Full original Japanese texts in Appendix D of the companion Japanese-language version.

D.1 余りを地域で受ける仕組み—A scheme for the region to absorb surplus D.2 余剰を地域で受ける—Absorbing surplus at the regional level (1) D.3 余剰を地域で受ける—Absorbing surplus at the regional level (2) D.4 余剰を地域で受け止める—Catching surplus at the regional level D.5 余剰を面で受ける仕組み—A scheme to absorb surplus area-wide D.6 余りを面で受ける仕組み—A scheme to absorb leftovers area-wide D.7 余りを面で受け止める—Catching leftovers area-wide D.8 余剰を地域で受ける—Absorbing surplus at the regional level (3) D.9 地域で余剰を受け止める—The region catching surplus D.10 地域で余りをつなぐ—Connecting leftovers within the region